

Language Rights in the South African Constitution

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Abstract

The Constitution of the Republic of South Africa entrenches the right to mother tongue use in several ways. The importance accorded to language rights is manifest in the fact that a separate and detailed section on language exists in the constituent and formal provisions of the first chapter. Section 3 declares eleven languages "official South African languages at national level". Further subsections entrench the right to use the official languages vis-à-vis national and provincial administrative bodies. Linguistic rights also form part of the Bill of Rights of Chapter 2, and chapter 7 on judicial authority and the administration of justice.

The provisions on language are best placed within the larger context of language policy in South Africa. Language rights are therefore subject to restrictions, i.e. where the exercise of a right may be limited to "where practicable". Using the example of four relevant cases decided by the Constitutional Court of South Africa, the scope of the language provisions can be determined, in particular by examining how these rights are limited. It is argued that the Court has so far interpreted language rights restrictively by rigorously applying the limitations where possible. It is suggested that the Court's prudent approach must be understood within a socio-economic context in which the position of the colonial languages, and English in particular, makes it largely impossible to realise the equitable use of the African languages to the extent that the Constitutional text promises.

1. Multilingualism, language policy and language legislation

All the polities of the world are, in varying degrees, multilingual - groups of speakers of differing mother-tongues coexist within the same state boundaries. In some cases, different ethno-linguistic communities enjoy the same political and cultural, including linguistic, rights by association in a federal polity.¹ Migratory movements across state boundaries may naturally contribute to multilingualism. However, more often the formation of present day states involved

¹ The now defunct Federal Republic of Yugoslavia and the Swiss Confederation can be counted amongst them.

the subjugation of linguistic communities by a militarily more formidable group. The colonial state, from which the majority of modern states, including the Republic of South Africa have descended is the prime example of this type.

Language policies whether overt or less precisely formulated are the way a state's politico-legal system responds to resulting linguistic heterogeneity. In many post-colonial nations language policy is politically sensitive, for claims to language equality are often part of, or perceived to be part of a wider call for a change in the distribution of material wealth and political power.² Language policies are best characterised with respect to their impact on disadvantaged languages. Bearing this in mind they can be situated along axes with extreme poles:³ Promotion of linguistic heterogeneity versus assimilation, with intermediate stages of toleration and permission; degree of overtness versus covertness⁴, which is closely related to the distinction between *de jure* and *de facto*; endoglossic versus exoglossic (involving the use of an indigenous as opposed to a non-indigenous official language, usually a former colonial language⁵; monolingual versus multilingual (the number of official languages)⁶.

Language legislation is the legal manifestation of some of the political choices involving language. It is a feature of an overt (*de jure*) language policy. Legislation on language can be characterised along functional lines taking factors such as aims or scope into account. Amongst the former we find an "officialising" - i.e. legislating language use in the public domain - or a standardising function – i.e. legislating the use of a particular variety of a designated language. The scope of language legislation can be defined by territoriality – i.e. legislating the use of designated languages in specified territorial units - or personality – i.e. where the right to use a language is part of one's personal law.⁷

The language policy that a state pursues can, amongst other factors, be examined by looking at the translation of these policies into legal realities. These may vary greatly. On one end states such as South Africa, Switzerland or Canada have entrenched language provisions in their constitutions while states like Côte d'Ivoire or Burkina Faso have declaratory language provisions in their constitution with parliamentary legislation giving substance to specific language policy aims. On the other end, states with a multilingual population may have no language legislation at all with a covert policy of assimilation to the dominant language – like, for example, some federal states of the United States of America. South Africa's constitutional language provisions are unique in the African context because of the number of languages

² see Alastair Pennycook (1994) *The Cultural Politics of English as an International Language*. London & New York: Longman, p. 15 ff

³ Tove Skutnabb-Kangas & Robert Phillipson, "Linguistic Human Rights, Past and Present", p 79-80, in Tove Skutnabb-Kangas & Robert Phillipson (1994), *Linguistic Human Rights*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter.

⁴ *ibid.*, p 79

⁵ Bernd Heine (1982) *Sprachpolitik in Afrika*. Hamburg: Helmut Buske Verlag

⁶ *ibid*

⁷ see Turi in, Tove Skutnabb-Kangas & Robert Phillipson (1994), *Linguistic Human Rights*. Berlin: Mouton de Gruyter

involved and because they are more than declaratory – they actually confer rights on individuals that can be invoked in the courts. The South African example may therefore serve well to show the interrelationship between language policy and legislation.

2. Language policy and language legislation in South Africa

The South African Constitutions of 1909, 1961 and 1983 provided for equality of the two official languages Afrikaans (or Dutch in the 1909 Constitution) and English. This meant that the use of either language was permitted in any setting. Additionally, past constitutions specifically spelt out the contexts in which both languages had to be used simultaneously – publications, proceedings and records of Parliament and national government. The political power of Afrikaans-speaking whites had led to a rapid development of Afrikaans, formerly considered a debased variety of standard Dutch by Afrikaans-speakers and speakers of European languages alike, with great strides undertaken in corpus and status planning allowing Afrikaans to be used in all formal domains alongside English.

Not surprisingly, there was no constitutional protection of language rights pertaining to African⁸ languages. The state's policy with respect to African languages was ambivalent. On one hand, there was no interest in promoting African languages to be used in the functioning of government similar to Afrikaans since political enfranchisement of black South Africans was not envisaged. On the other hand, the Apartheid policy of "separate development" had the ideological corollary of allowing, in fact promoting a degree of linguistic autonomy even if solely aimed at furthering ethnic separatism amongst black people so as to prevent unified political resistance. There was, therefore, a limited use of African languages in some contexts⁹ (grounded in corresponding legislation) with English and Afrikaans being imposed as the primary languages of the formal domain. In this sense, South Africa pursued a typical colonial language policy with a clear hierarchy of languages mirroring the distribution of political power.

The language provisions of the 1994 Interim Constitution, consolidated by the 1996 Final Constitution, are the attempt to lay the foundations of an equitable language policy after decades of misuse of language *"for the purposes of exploitation, domination or division"*.¹⁰ Yet, the post-Apartheid Constitutions also represent a compromise between conflicting interests on the one hand - the appeasement of fears of white South Africans about a denigration of the

⁸ I use the term "African" to characterise the languages spoken on the territory of South Africa before colonisation and "colonial" for Afrikaans and English, although the latter two also serve as mother-tongues to groups that were oppressed within the colonial structure, and Afrikaans, being a language that evolved on African soil, can certainly be called an African language. However, the failure to distinguish between African as opposed to colonial languages would amount to playing down the role that Afrikaans and English played in colonial exploitation in South Africa.

⁹ For example in primary and secondary education within the segregated system of "bantus education".

¹⁰ S 3(9)(c), interim Constitution.

status of Afrikaans and English - and a genuine attempt to enhance the status and use of the African languages on the other.

3. Language rights in the Interim and the Final Constitution

The Interim Constitution (IC) of the Republic of South Africa came into force in April 1994 and was superseded by the Final Constitution (FC) in 1996. The FC is the supreme law of South Africa with the exclusive jurisdiction pertaining to the Constitutional Court to strike down unconstitutional legislation. Being inflexible and entrenched, any amendment to the Constitution requires prescribed legislative procedures involving special majorities in Parliament.¹¹ The FC contains provisions on the organisation of the national and provincial executives, legislatures, the judiciary and the administration of justice and a Bill of Rights. The system of government installed by the Constitution may be described as a mixed presidential and parliamentary system. The FC contains no express mention as to whether South Africa is a unitary or federal state. The provincial legislatures possess a non-exclusive competence to legislate on an enumerated list of policy areas, notwithstanding Parliament's right to enact concurrent (and overriding) legislation under certain circumstances. Amongst these provincial legislative powers can be found the right of provincial legislatures to enact language legislation subject to certain conditions.

In view of a long history of human rights abuse during white-minority rule, one of the centrepieces of the South African Constitution is the Bill of Rights contained in Chapter 2. Apart from the enumerated substantive rights, the Bill of Rights contains four operational provisions. The application clause (s 8) entrenches the vertical applicability of Chapter 2, the suspension clause (s) provides for the suspension of Chapter 2 rights in a state of emergency.

The limitation clause of s 36 allows for the limitation of rights contained in Chapter 2 *"in terms of law of general application to the extent that the limitation is reasonable and justifiable in an open and democratic society based on human dignity, equality and freedom [...]"*.¹²

The general limitation clause can only be fully appreciated in combination with the interpretation clause of s 39, which provides statutory support for a teleological approach to constitutional interpretation. In interpreting Chapter 2 rights courts are directed to *"promote the values that underlie an open and democratic society based on human dignity, equality and freedom"*¹³. In that process, South African courts are also directed to have regard to public

¹¹ Basson, Dion (1994), *South Africa's Interim Constitution – Text and Notes*. Capetown: Juta & Co Ltd, p. xxiv

¹² S 36(1)

¹³ S 39(1)(a)

international law applicable to the protection of the rights entrenched in the Bill and are permitted to have recourse to foreign case law.¹⁴

4. The language provisions of the Constitution

In the FC, substantive language rights are contained in s 6 of chapter 1 (founding provisions) and in s 9 (3), s 29(2), s 30 and s 31(1) of Chapter 2 (Bill of Rights). Procedural language rights are contained in s 35(3)(k) (Bill of Rights).

Section 6, FC (Languages)

S 6(1), FC declares eleven South African languages to be the official national languages of the Republic on an equal standing.¹⁵ S 6(2) directs the state to engage in status planning in order to enhance the status and use of languages with a "historically diminished use and status", i.e. the African languages. The provisions of s 6, FC are less far-reaching than those of its predecessor, s 3 of the 1994 Interim Constitution. For example, s 3 (2) of the IC contained a non-diminution clause and embodied a maximalist approach to the creation of language equality. The provision first made it unconstitutional for the legislator to diminish existing rights¹⁶ pertaining to any of the national languages. In effect, this meant that the use of English and Afrikaans as the languages of government business, the judiciary and Parliament would not be curtailed or replaced by another of the official languages.¹⁷ Within the "Bantustan" system of pseudo-federalism during Apartheid, most of African languages enjoyed the legal status of official language alongside English and Afrikaans on the regional level. On that level, the non-diminution requirement also applied to these languages. But beyond that, s 3(2), IC gave the legislator the power to extend the status and use of these regional languages to the national level, i.e. the formerly exclusive domain of the English and Afrikaans.

Additionally, s 3(3), IC was also removed from the final text. This provision was of central importance because it gave the individual the right to use an official language of personal choice in state-subject interaction even if subject to a limitation – "*wherever practicable*".¹⁸ Also, the clause gave "official language" an additional dimension alongside its meaning as such

¹⁴ S 39(1)(b),(c)

¹⁵ The languages are Sepedi, Sesotho, Setswana, siSwati, Tshivenda, Xitsonga, Afrikaans, English, isiNdebele, isiXhosa and isiZulu. There are of course many more languages spoken in South Africa. S 6(5)(b) explicitly states that respect for these smaller languages and their development shall be promoted.

¹⁶ i.e. rights from pre-1994 Apartheid era legislation that had not been repealed. The South African "compromise" only allows for a selective repeal of legislation dating from the Apartheid era.

¹⁷ The only replacement candidates being the African languages, this provision certainly had a strong element of appeasement of the white community.

¹⁸ S 3(3) reads: "*Wherever practicable, a person shall have the right to use and to be addressed in his or her dealings with any public administration at the national level of government in any official South African language of his or her choice*".

language that may be used for the purposes of government by a national and provincial government¹⁹

It is remarkable that in pursuit of linguistic equality, both s 3(1), IC and s 6(1), FC declare all the languages concerned *national* official languages, in spite of a regional or ethnically restricted distribution of some of them and the use as inter-ethnic and supra-regional *linguae francae* of others.²⁰ Notwithstanding, the socio-linguistic and geographic distribution of the African languages is accommodated within the system of devolved government peculiar to South Africa. S 6(3)(a), FC provides that, "*the national and provincial governments may use any particular official languages for the purposes of government*", subject to the limitation, "*taking into account usage, practicality, expense, regional circumstances and the balance of the needs and preferences of the population as a whole or in the province concerned*" and the direction to use at least two of the national languages for this purpose. The margin of appreciation of "*usage*" and "*preferences*" is extended to municipal authorities in s 6(3)(b), interestingly enough without s 6(3)(a) explicitly giving municipalities the discretionary power of language choice that it gives to the national and provincial governments.²¹ This, or a similar provision was not contained in the Interim Constitution and its inclusion appears to be a consequence of one of the cases decided by the Constitutional Court, as will be shown.

Discretionary powers with respect to regional differentiation of language policy and legislation were already contained in s 3 of the Interim Constitution, albeit with a fundamental difference. S 3(5) permitted a super-majority of a provincial *legislature* to adopt any of the national official languages as *official language(s) of the province* – mirroring the national legislature's right to do so. In this context S 6(5), FC is noteworthy because it lays out a set of general principles which shall govern language legislation and thereby gives a blue print of language policy within the Constitution. A statutory body, the Pan South African Language Board is set up for the task of status and corpus planning. The legal position of the African languages of South Africa has therefore improved dramatically in comparison to former constitutions. Nonetheless, the scaling-down of the more ambitious provisions of the Interim Constitution is amongst other factors a consequence of the reluctance the courts showed in applying these generously formulated rights in case law. This will subsequently be shown.

Section 9(3) and 9(4) FC (Equality)

S 9 is the central equality provision of the Bill of rights. Ss 9(3) and 9(4), FC forbid amongst other forms of discrimination, unfair direct and indirect vertical and horizontal discrimination on

¹⁹ cf. s 6(3)(a) FC

²⁰ isiZulu and English in particular and to a slightly lesser extent Sesotho, Afrikaans and isiXhosa are supra-regional *linguae francae*, while the remaining languages are primarily regional languages.

²¹ This subsection seems to be a direct consequence of *Louw v Transitional Local Council of Greater Germiston* 1997 8 BCLR 1062 (W) In that case it became clear that the competences of local authority regarding language policy were not clear under the interim Constitution, where they had not been specifically mentioned. The Louw case is discussed below.

grounds of language.²² In the Interim Constitution, S 8(2) covered the same right. S 9(3) is subject to an inherent limitation, namely "*unfairly*", and the entire s 9 to the limitation contained in s 9(2), which leaves enough space for differential treatment and provides the legal grounds for affirmative action legislation.²³

S 29(2) (Education)

S 29(2) FC entrenches the right, "to receive education in the official language or languages of their choice in public educational institutions", subject to a limitation - "*where that education is reasonably practicable*". The inherent limitation of practicality may be interpreted as involving pedagogical and financial factors.²⁴ The Interim Constitution had an equivalent provision in s 32(b) IC. An additional provision, s 32(c), containing the right to establish educational institutions based on a common language was not carried over into the final text.

Section 30 (Language and culture)

S 30 (S 31 of the Interim Constitution) entrenches the individual right to use of language of one's choice as a fundamental right within the Bill of Rights.²⁵ It thereby provides the foundation on which the language provisions of s 6 FC rest.

FC Section s 35(3)(k)

S 35 FC (which supercedes ss 25(1)(a) and 25(3)(i) IC) contains a detailed list of procedural rights in criminal proceedings within which is contained the right "*to be tried in a language that the accused person understands, or if that is not practicable, to have the proceedings interpreted in that language*"²⁶. This right therefore once again contains an inherent limitation – "practicality". In the now superseded Interim Constitution the chapter on the judiciary and the administration of justice contained a provision which was the equivalent to s 35 in civil proceedings. S 107(1) IC entrenches the right of a litigant, an accused or a witness to use a South African language of his or her choice in court. Additionally, s 107(2) states that court records shall be kept in any official language subject to the non-diminution of existing rights

²² S 9(3) reads, "*The state may not unfairly discriminate directly or indirectly against anyone on one or more grounds, including race, gender, sex, pregnancy, marital status, ethnic or social origin, colour, sexual orientation, age, disability, religion, conscience, belief, culture, language and birth.*" S 9(4) specifies that 9(3) also applies horizontally: "*No person may unfairly discriminate directly or indirectly against anyone on one or more grounds in terms of subsection (3).*"

²³ S 9(2) reads: "*[...] To promote the achievement of equality, legislative and other measures designed to protect or advance persons, or categories of persons, disadvantaged by unfair discrimination may be taken.*"

²⁴ Chaskalson, Kentridge, Klaaren, Marcus, Woolman (1998), "*Constitutional Law of South Africa*". Cape Town: Juta & Co. p 38-13

²⁵ S 31: "*Every person has the right to use the language and to participate in the cultural life of their choice [...].*"

²⁶ S 35(3)(k)

relating to language.²⁷ Interestingly enough, s 107 was not included in the final Constitutional text.

In summary, the language provisions of the Interim Constitution appear far-reaching. They cover substantive as well as procedural rights. Language legislation in the Constitution has an "officialising" function and a territorial and personal dimension²⁸. Relying on the constitutional provisions alone, the language provisions entrench an overt, endoglossic, multilingual language policy with the relevant languages enjoying de jure recognition as official languages. However, only an analysis of the interpretation of the language provisions by the Constitutional Court can provide a more adequate picture of their legal significance. In particular because inherent limitations and the application of the general limitation clause have the potential to significantly restrict the exercise of these rights.

5. The comparative perspective

Constitutional language legislation may be divided into different types. A distinction can be made between constitutions that declare a single language and those that declare several languages to be the official language of the state.²⁹ In "mono-lingual constitutions" the official language is then the only legally valid medium of communication for the business of government and administration, the judiciary and the educational system, i.e. the formal domain. In the majority of post-colonial states the official language is identical with the national language of the former coloniser, a language which is usually nobody's mother-tongue. Nevertheless, in most monolingual constitutions of post-colonial nations, provisions are made for the recognition and promotion of the indigenous languages.³⁰ In African constitutional terminology these are called "national languages". These "promotion clauses" may range from

²⁷ This meant that the practice of keeping records in either Afrikaans or English would not have been affected, while one or several of the African languages could have been used additionally.

²⁸ The right to be tried in a language understood by the accused as granted by s 35(3)(k) FC. Had the right to use an official language in state-subject intercourse within the entire territory as entrenched in s 3(3) IC been retained in the final Constitution, the scope of the personal dimension would have been much wider.

²⁹ Some long established nation states with a history of linguistic homogenisation may have political boundaries that are relatively coterminous with linguistic ones - or at least perceived to be so. There the constitutional text may not even contain a declaratory statement on what the national language is since the language of the majority group implicitly qualifies as the "national" language. This may be the case in spite of the existence of considerable linguistic minorities within these nation states. (cf. France, Germany, Poland). In some of these states ordinary parliamentary legislation may deal with language diversity with regards to education, state-subject intercourse and other areas.

³⁰ Notable exceptions are the constitutions of those African countries in which the former colonial and official language has been replaced by an indigenous language. For example, in the Constitution of Algeria Arabic alone is declared the official and national language whereas the other languages spoken in the territory are not even mentioned.

purely declaratory statements to an obligation imposed on the state to actively promote the use and status of the national languages.

For example, s 2 of the Constitution of Gabon declares French the official working language, while the state *"works for the protection and promotion of the national languages"*.³¹ S 4 of the 2003 Constitution of the Democratic Republic of Congo declares French the official language. The four most widely spoken languages of the country are declared *"national languages"* a designation with no legal implications.³² The 1990 Constitution of Mozambique declares Portuguese the official language, while *"the State recognises the value of the national languages and shall promote their development [...]"*. Similar "promotion provisions" can be found in the Constitutions of Guinea, Indonesia, Thailand, and Tanzania.

A different approach is exemplified by the Constitutions of Mali and Burkina Faso. Both Constitutions declare French the official language, but they also contain precise directions amounting to more than a statement on promotion of the national languages. They provide a constitutional basis for parliamentary legislation with two specific aims: the commitment to promotion of the national languages *and* their future conversion into official languages³³ - in reality a language policy programme. In practice, this means that parliamentary legislation in both countries is to pave the way for the extension of the functions of the national languages by legislating for their use in formal domains formerly reserved for the official language such as education, broadcasting or local government.

What nevertheless unites all the aforementioned Constitutions is the absence of individual or group rights relating to language that are invocable before the courts.³⁴ Therefore, the dichotomy of official vs. national language is problematic because the concept of the national language is in most cases, void of legal meaning.

Constitutions declaring two or more languages as official languages are far fewer both within and outside of Africa. In fact, there is a close correspondence between the political system of a state and the likelihood of a "plurilingual" constitution. In federal nation-states, internal boundaries between federal units are often largely coterminous with language boundaries. It is therefore possible for federal governments to opt for one or several of the official languages for use in the business of government and administration, and education, as long as speakers of the remaining official languages do not find their language rights infringed.

³¹ S 2: *"La République gabonaise adopte le français comme langue officielle de travail. En outre elle oeuvre pour la protection et la promotion des langues nationales."*

³² S 4: *"Les langues nationales sont : le kikongo, le lingala, le swahili et le tshiluba. La langue officielle est le français."*

³³ S 35 of the Burkinabè Constitution reads, *"la langue officielle est le français. La loi fixe les modalités de promotion et d'officialisation des langues nationales."*

³⁴ Usually, even the choice of national languages is not comprehensive but rather includes only the larger languages or those of politically dominant peoples within the territory. In Togo for example, a small minority language, Kabye, was declared a national language because the President and the political elite were its native speakers. The choice of national languages is therefore politically highly significant, even if lacking in legal content.

For example, the Swiss Constitution recognises four national languages, German, French, Italian and Romansh, three of which are declared official languages, i.e. working languages of the confederation.³⁵ The remaining language Romansh (a small minority language) is an official language of the confederation in dealings with mother-tongue speakers, and therefore part of those citizens' personal law.³⁶ The cantons, i.e. federal units, are entitled to choose their official languages with the margin of appreciation of having to take the linguistic composition of the population into account and having special consideration for linguistic minorities.³⁷

The federal state of India has a slightly more complicated plurilingual constitution due to the superposition of the colonial language English on an already existing hegemonic indigenous language, namely Hindi. It nevertheless bears resemblance to South Africa in the amount of languages involved, albeit with an important distinction: federal units may declare their respective majority language(s) to be *federal* official languages only *in addition* to at least one of the two *national* official languages English and Hindi.³⁸

In the African context, Tanzania deserves special attention. The post-independence Constitution of 1965 and subsequent amendments contain no language provisions. After independence, the vast majority of African states opted for a language policy that retained and even enhanced the use of the colonial languages. The Tanzanian state, however, declared Kiswahili national language and engaged in a radical expansion of Kiswahili into all functional areas except tertiary education, driven by secondary legislation. The retention of English as a working language was an acknowledgment of the existing cultural, political, social and intellectual ties with the former colonial power and other Commonwealth nations. However, the radical drive to replace English by Kiswahili in Tanzania in such a short time was only possible due to the unique socio-linguistic make-up of the country in which Kiswahili has a long history of serving as an inter-ethnic lingua franca. The functional expansion of Kiswahili has however not only occurred at the expense of English. It has also led to a wide-spread language shift by the post-independence generation in favour of Kiswahili and to the detriment of many smaller languages, some of which have all but disappeared.³⁹ Nevertheless, the endogenous language policy of Tanzania, with its enhancement of the status and use of an African language has served as a point of reference for many African intellectuals in their call for similar policies and legislation in their respective countries.

³⁵ S 4: "Die Landessprachen sind Deutsch, Französisch, Italienisch und Rätoromanisch".

³⁶ S 70(1): "Die Amtssprachen des Bundes sind Deutsch, Französisch und Italienisch. Im Verkehr mit Personen rätoromanischer Sprache ist auch das Rätoromanische Amtssprache des Bundes."

³⁷ S 70(2): "Die Kantone bestimmen ihre Amtssprachen. Um das Einvernehmen zwischen den Sprachgemeinschaften zu wahren, achten sie auf die herkömmliche sprachliche Zusammensetzung der Gebiete und nehmen Rücksicht auf die angestammten sprachlichen Minderheiten. "

³⁸ In fact the section governing the status of English is very similar to s 3, non-diminution requirement of the South African interim Constitution, and may have provided a model for the South African FC.

³⁹ See e.g. Ladefoged, Peter (1992) Another View of Endangered Languages. *Language* 68(4). 809–811.

On the whole, a few conclusions can be drawn from a comparison of language legislation. The vast majority of post-colonial states have mono-lingual constitutions declaring either the colonial language or an indigenous language as official language, much in line with the dominant state structure, the unitary state. The constitutional status of the other languages ranges from symbolic recognition to provisions for active promotion. No mono-lingual constitution however confers rights on the speakers of national, indigenous languages that can be invoked in the courts.

The SA Constitution's language provisions therefore embody the effort to eradicate this structural injustice. By conferring the same legal status on the African languages of South Africa as the one enjoyed by the colonial languages English and Afrikaans, the Constitution redresses the injustice caused by exoglossic language policies, where differential access to the colonial language leads to educational, political and social marginalisation of majority of South Africa's population.⁴⁰ By creating complete legal equality between all the major languages of South Africa, the Constitution also strives for a balance between the different constituent peoples of the Republic. This is reinforced by the provisions allowing for a provincial discretion in language legislation and policy.

6. The interpretation of the language provisions by the Constitutional Court⁴¹

Case law shows that the language provisions of the Constitution are, however, applied rather conservatively. In *S v Ngubane*⁴², probably the earliest case relating to language rights to reach the Constitutional Court, the appellant claimed that he had been deprived of the Chapter 2, procedural right (S 25(3)(i)) to be tried in a language intelligible to him or to have proceedings interpreted to him. The proceedings had been interpreted to the appellant in Tswana which, being a Zulu speaker, he did not understand. A proposal by the attorney-general to subsequently interpret the tape-recorded proceedings into Zulu was rejected and the proceedings accordingly set aside.

In *Mthetwa v De Bruin NO*,⁴³ the appellant invoked s 6(1) of the Final Constitution⁴⁴ which declares Zulu one of the official languages in order to have the entire proceedings conducted in Zulu. The magistrate had refused the application and ordered the trial to be conducted either in

⁴⁰ Apartheid was of course the primary reason for differential access to educational resources and political participation in South Africa – a system much unlike the amorphous structural injustice caused by systems of elite reproduction in non-caste class societies.

⁴¹ The text of the final constitution contains slight differences in some of the language provisions. Wherever this applies, reference will be made to any changes in the discussion of the cases.

⁴² 1995 (1) BCLR 121 (T)

⁴³ 1998 (3) BCLR 336 (N)

⁴⁴ S 6(1) of the final constitution is identical to s 3(1) of the interim constitution

English or Afrikaans. On review the applicant sought a declaration of unconstitutionality and an order to have the trial conducted in Zulu.

The court argued that s 35(3)(k)⁴⁵ of the final Constitution guaranteed the applicant the right to "have the proceedings interpreted into Zulu for his benefit", but not to have proceedings conducted in Zulu. Predictably, the court raised the argument of impracticality in justifying this interpretation. It was argued that the vast majority of magistrates, prosecutors and judges was either English or Afrikaans speaking⁴⁶, and that there was no recorder ?? capable of transcribing a record in Zulu. Although the court conceded that 98% of the accused and witnesses in the relevant regional court were on the other hand Zulu speaking, the court nevertheless concluded that "*it was not and is not practicable for the applicant to have the proceedings in the Regional Court [...] conducted and recorded in the Zulu language*".⁴⁷ Once again the limitation of the right was not achieved through the s 33 general limitation clause but by way of the inherent limitation of s 35(3)(k). The issue raised by the applicant in this case of course goes to the heart of the underlying political issue that the percentage of black South Africans within the judiciary is grossly out of proportion with population figures. This shows that the question of "practicality" is to be seen within the social and political context.

In *S v Matomela*⁴⁸ the Court examined a lower court's decision to use Xhosa as the language of proceedings - the reverse situation of *Mthethwa v De Bruin NO*, where the applicant had insisted on the use of his mother tongue in the proceedings. The lower court had decided against the use of English and simultaneous interpretation to the accused due to the temporary unavailability of interpreters. Contrary to *Mthethwa*, this was possible because all the parties to the proceedings as well as the presiding officer were Xhosa speaking. The decision was justified by reference to ss 6(1), read with 6(2), 6(4) of the Final Constitution⁴⁹, which declares Xhosa one of the official languages of South Africa and provides for the non-diminution of existing rights relating to language, as well as S 35(3)(k) of the Final Constitution.

In the opinion of the Constitutional Court the decision of the lower court was "*fair and reasonable in the circumstances*", particularly given the absence of legislation on official languages for the courts. The Court was of the opinion that the absence of legislation to that effect was in need of a remedy because the lack of translation facilities was due to increase while the costs of remedying that situation and would be "enormous". The Court in fact opined

45 This section is the equivalent of s 25(3)(i) with one important difference. S 35(3)(k) contains an internal limitation. An accused has the right to be tried in a language he or she understands or "if that is not practicable, to have the proceedings interpreted in that language." S 25(3)(i) of the interim Constitution uses the phrase "failing this" instead.

46 The figures given for Zulu speaking members of the judiciary in the Natal province were the following: 81 prosecutors of a total of 256; 4 regional court magistrates of a total of 37; 6 advocates out of a total of 41, and 1 judge of a total of 22. Ibid 337.

47 Ibid 338.

48 1998 (3) BCLAR 339 (Ck)

49 The equivalent of ss 3(1), 3(2) and 3(4) of the interim constitution.

that the designation of an official court language was urgent and that such a language "should be one which can be understood by all court officials irrespective of mother tongue" - an obvious playdoyer for an English only policy.

In *Louw v Transitional Local Council of Greater Germiston*⁵⁰, the local authority of Greater Germiston had passed a resolution declaring English as the "written and spoken language of the [...] council". The applicant Mr Louw, an Afrikaans speaker sought a declaration of incompatibility with the language rights entrenched in Chapter 2 of the Interim Constitution and a mandatory injunction/ prohibition, setting aside the resolution.

S 31, the right invoked, was however held to have no bearing on the "untrammelled right of any body, private or statutory to regulate its own procedure", which "includes [...] the right to select a language of government or debate ". S 3, on official languages, was found to be of more relevance for the case. The court reasoned that the right for the national and provincial legislatures to choose official languages to be used within their area of competence (ss 3(4), 3(5), 3(8)) did not explicitly extend to local authorities. This right was however seen in the light of s 3(9). This section provides amongst others that language legislation on "the use of languages at any level of government" (s 3(9)(f)) shall be subject to the principle of "non-diminution of rights relating to language [...] existing at the commencement of this Constitution". The reference to "any level of government " was found to include local government.

Having established the applicability of the constitutional provisions of s 3 and s 3(9) in particular, the court however found that the section could not be invoked because the local government's "resolution" was not equivalent to "legislation". Therefore the court could avoid the issue of considering whether the local government's resolution was justifiable within the margin of appreciation contained in s 3(8), namely "taking into account questions of usage, practicality and expense" and/or the general limitations clause of s 33. The applicant would therefore have faced formidable barriers even if the resolution had been found to be legislation.

7. The protection of constitutional language rights in South Africa

The protection of language rights in the judicial process are taken seriously by the Constitutional Court and the provisions are undisputedly useful in achieving procedural justice. A party to litigation will therefore always be able to demand proceedings to be translated into his or her mother tongue as can be seen in *S v Ngubane*. Notwithstanding, the references to costs and delays and practicality show that the rights contained in ss 25(3)(i) and 107(2) have been interpreted restrictively to mean access to interpretation facilities - a basic amenity that any state governed by the rule of law provides to its citizens

⁵⁰ 1997 (8) BCLR 1062 (W)

Moreover, *S v Matomela* also shows that there is support for an English only policy amongst the judiciary, with the possibility of legislation declaring English the sole "administrative" language of courts not too far removed.⁵¹ *Louw* shows that the language rights entrenched in S 3 on official languages will also be interpreted restrictively. Successfully invoking these rights will prove to be difficult due to the inherent limitations contained in ss 3(3) and 3(6) of the Interim Constitution⁵² and the margin of appreciation contained in s 3(8)⁵³.

Moreover the non-diminution requirement contained in ss 3(2) and 3(9) contains a further barrier. During the Apartheid years, speakers of African languages had no language rights - their languages were "diminished" in status relative to that of the two official languages Afrikaans and English. The latter two languages, are therefore in the favourable position of having benefited from official government policy for nearly a century and are, and English in particular is, the only language(s) whose status and usage in the formal domain remain unrivalled. However, as a consequence of these provisions "legislation as well as official policy and practice, in relation to the use of languages at any level of government"⁵⁴ can therefore only extend the rights relating to usage of the African languages to the level of those enjoyed by the two colonial languages but not diminish the status of the latter two in achieving the goal of language parity - in the light of the socio-linguistic dominance of the colonial languages a wholly unrealistic venture.⁵⁵ In practice therefore, many of the efforts to extend these rights will fail due to the inherent limitations of practicality and expense contained in the language provisions - thereby creating a circularity of interpretation which will be difficult to overcome.⁵⁶ The non-diminution requirement has been dropped from the text of the Final Constitution. It remains to be seen whether this will open the door to a more diverse official language policy, particularly in the provinces, or whether the removal of the "favoured status" of Afrikaans and English will

51 The statement of the regional head of the justice department of Western Cape, a province with a predominantly Afrikaans-speaking population, in which he proposes to use English as the sole language of court records lends support to this view ("English only urged for court records", Sunday Times, 17-10-1999). Also, the ongoing debate in Parliament to publish parliamentary records in English only fits in with the developing attitude of "realism" with respect to language legislation and policy.

52 The right to use official languages in dealings with the national and provincial administration respectively is subject to the limitation "wherever practicable".

53 The discretionary power of the national and provincial legislatures to conduct the business of government in one of the official languages may be exercised "taking into account questions of usage, practicality and expense."

⁵⁴ S 3(9) interim Constitution.

⁵⁵ A practical consequence of the non-diminution provision is that all rights pertaining to English and Afrikaans through pre-1994 legislation are still in force. This means, for example that all national and provincial legislation must be published in English and Afrikaans in accordance with the dual official language provisions of previous constitutions. Any effort to additionally publish legislation in more than one or two of the remaining nine official languages will be subject to the margin of appreciation of s 3(8) of the interim Constitution. The more realistic option of replacing publishing in Afrikaans in provinces where it is a minority language by that in an African majority language would be unconstitutional.

⁵⁶ So far, the Constitutional Court has not tried to construe language rights more broadly and anchor a limitation within the s 33 general limitations clause which has a two-staged test with a higher threshold.

make considerations of practicality pave the way for an English only policy for administrative purposes.

Seen in the light of the observations made above, this lends weight to the assumption that the language provisions in the Interim Constitution are primarily politico-symbolic in content. Although the constitutional entrenchment of the language provisions theoretically creates more far-reaching rights, the restrictive interpretation of these rights and socio-linguistic reality makes the situation very similar to that of other African countries. In most African nations, the colonial language is the sole official language, while African languages are given political recognition as "national" languages in the constitution with no rights attached to them.

8. Conclusion

The ambitious and far-reaching language provisions of the South African Constitution have been curtailed by the courts. But this does not amount to judicial activism on their part – the judiciary seems to be reacting to changes in the wider political context where calls for an English only policy will probably win out – the power to legislate for the exclusive use of a particular language *"for the purposes of the functioning of the government"* has been given to Parliament by virtue of s 3(8) and will certainly be used to regulate language use in court proceedings and might be used to introduce English as the sole language of business within the entire administrative system.

This development shows the limits of the rights culture embodied in the Constitution. Political and socio-economic factors will not allow for the admittedly noble aim of language equality beyond "parity of esteem". In the real world English has become the dominant language of the formal domain and has also increased greatly as a language of inter-ethnic communication in South Africa. Educational policies provide for the use of English as the main language of teaching with a subordinate, regionally varying role accorded to the other official languages. Most importantly, the fact that South Africa has a highly internationalised capitalist economy contributes to the rapid expansion of English and Anglo-American culture into all sectors of society. Under these conditions it will become ever more "impractical" to legally enforce many of the language provisions of the Constitution and it is submitted that the constitutional provisions might at some point be altered to reflect these realities.

The language provisions of the Constitution represent a bold step but it has been shown that socio-linguistic realities make the realisation of these rights nearly impossible in many respects. The potentially far-reaching legal provisions on language would have only made sense if set within the larger context of an equally fundamental socio-economic change in which not only the dominance of English and Afrikaans as languages but also the economic dominance of the speakers of these languages would have been curtailed. In countries such as

Indonesia, the Republic of Guinea or Algeria in which the status of the indigenous languages vis-à-vis the colonial language was enhanced, fundamental changes in language policy went hand in hand with radical political and socio-economic change.

In the vast majority of African countries the transition to independence was not disruptive and continuing economic and political dependence on the former colonising nations has led to the continuation of colonial language policies based on corresponding legislation. South Africa has committed itself to a path of gradual socio-economic change and redistribution. The restricted enforceability of the language provisions should therefore also be seen in this light. Unfortunately the existence of the language provisions raises hopes and expectations which cannot be fulfilled.